

The Post-socialist City, Between Inequality and Taking (Back the) Power

Nikolay Karkov, State University of New York at Cortland

Merve Bedir, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne

Pavel Yanchev, independent researcher

Abstract

With the East (the former Second World) having lost much of its scholarly appeal since the end of the Cold War, texts about, let alone special issues on, the post-socialist city in Eastern Europe continue to be relatively sparse in urban studies. Based on the Forum on Urban Inequalities held in the city of Sofia in 2022, this dossier seeks to address this lacuna, from a wide variety of theoretical and methodological perspectives. The featured articles explore the promises and challenges of socially engaged architecture, the neoliberalization of housing and the struggles against it, and the difficulties of even defining what a (post)socialist city is or could be within urban studies. The issue makes contributions to ongoing debates on the political economy of the contemporary city, the right to housing and the housing as a commons, and comparative and global urbanism.

Keywords

urban studies, urban inequality, post-socialist city, political economy, housing

This dossier of texts is based on contributions to the Sofia Forum on “Urban Inequalities: from the Right to the City to Taking Control,” which took place in the Bulgarian capital on June 17-19, 2022. Organized by the Collective for Social Interventions (KOI), a local leftist organization of scholars and activists, the forum and its subsequent two iterations, “Future Cities, Future Climates: Urban Crises of Late Capitalism” (in 2023) and “Contested Heritage, Troubled Future: Memory Wars in the Urban Fabric (2024) respectively, have sought to produce ruptures in the neoliberal common sense while also helping build bridges among progressive activists, researchers, and policymakers in the region.¹ While we were not able to

¹ Founded as a non-governmental organisation in Sofia in 2013, KOI conducts socially engaged research, organises policy campaigns, and functions as a publishing house as well. The 2022 “Urban Inequalities” Forum

Corresponding author: Nikolay Karkov, State University of New York at Cortland, nkarkov@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5324-180X>

Authors:

Merve Bedir, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, bedirmerve@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-8820-3993>;

Pavel Yanchev, independent researcher, yanchev.pavel@gmail.com

receive all the texts we had originally solicited, the articles gathered in this special issue speak to a number of important debates on the problems of urbanity and the postsocialist city. Their shared ambition is the insistence on the relevance of thinking from and about Eastern Europe in discussions on inequality, urbanism and the city.

The first line of inquiry, running like a red thread through our special issue, draws heavily on a political economic critique of the (not only post-socialist) city as a crucial yet also contested site of capitalist accumulation. This line is not new but goes back to at least the mid-nineteenth century when a young Friedrich Engels was busy surveilling the “great towns” of industrial England. For Karl Marx’s future collaborator, those sprawling urban settlements were not only horrifying concentrations of abject poverty, dirt, and child exploitation but also an indispensable material basis for the emergence of the organized working-class movement (Engels, 1987). Yet while Marxists certainly hold no monopoly over critical discussions of the city (think of Élisée Reclus or Georg Simmel at the turn of the twentieth century for instance; Reclus, 2013; Simmel, 1950), it is only after the post-World War II period that this kind of critique would come fully into its own. By the late 1960s and as he probed the complexities of the unfolding “urban revolution,” Henri Lefebvre was insisting on the indispensable “right to the city,” in what would turn out to be an all-too-fragile post-war consensus (Lefebvre, 2000; 2003). The Marxist geography and urban studies that followed would contribute original concepts such as spatial fix, rent gap, or accumulation by dispossession, in an effort to address the complex articulations of the labor-capital conflict under urban conditions (e.g. Iles, 2023, pp. 67-80). Yet as David Harvey helpfully reminds us, we may never underestimate “the role played by the sensibility that arises out of the streets around us, the inevitable feeling of loss provoked by the demolitions, what happens when whole quarters ... get re-engineered ... coupled with the exhilaration or annoyance of street demonstrations about this or that” (Harvey, 2019, pp. x-xi).

While Harvey’s work has been particularly influential in Eastern Europe (Gagyi and Pósfai, 2023, pp. 86-87), it is precisely the changing sensibility of the “streets around us” that has both drawn on and extended the anti-capitalist critique of the now post-socialist cities in

sought to address topical issues in urban politics from the perspective of environmental inequalities, uneven access to municipal services and affordable housing, racial segregation, and public management reforms. The 2023 “Climate and the City” edition focused on thinking about how urban social issues and the escalating climate crisis braid together and what can be done to mitigate them, foregrounding the correlation between economic growth and environmental degradation. Lastly, the 2024 “Contested Heritage” iteration of the forum zoned in on sites of memory in the contemporary city, in light of the urban morphology of neoliberalism, the socialist and Ottoman legacies, and the role of popular culture in shaping the public memory of the urban environment, among others. For more information, see <https://koi-bg.org/en/category/events/>.

the region. Indeed, the often-radical makeover of Eastern European cities has been a veritable basket-case of neoliberal restructuring, with few of the palliatives still deployed in the “West”/global North. As capitals like Sofia have lost up to 30% of their former green spaces to a literal construction frenzy (Hirt, 2012, p. 56), as the Belgrade Waterfront mega-project has displaced over 200 families, along with the local railway and bus station (Vilenica, Florea, Popovici, and Pósfai, 2021, pp. 309-310), as the urban regeneration of “magnet cities” like Cluj has required the resettlement of the local racialized Roma population near a landfill (Vincze, in this issue), and as the dismantling of tenant protections in Athens has led to a spike in foreclosures in the city (Katerini, 2022, p. 234), it is hard to see (and even more, experience) the “post-socialist transition” as anything but a brutal assault on its people and their lived environments. The neoliberal urban counter-revolution has of course been met with growing resistance in the region, whether in the form of “Right to the City” initiatives, heritage protection protests, anti-eviction and refugee support organizing, socially engaged architecture (see Dragović in this issue), etc. Yet the wider impact of those movements and struggles continues to be hampered by both material and ideological barriers: from Eastern Europe’s semi-peripheral role in the capitalist world-system as provider of raw materials and cheap labor, to a still dominant capitalocentric and Western-centric common sense that quickly invokes the specter of communism in the face of any collectivist initiative.

A second set of debates to which this dossier speaks has to do with the situation of post-socialist housing in the region, including practices of commodification, financialization, eviction, and the struggles against them. In Eastern Europe in particular, those practices may sometimes appear heterogeneous and eclectic on the surface, even as they serve the same profit-driven logic facilitated by massive levels of indebtedness (see Pósfai and Sokol in this issue). No less importantly, engaging in, but also thinking about, those struggles has taken at least two significant forms in the region. On the one hand, there has been an effort to think about housing as one of the focal points of urban commoning and as a form of cohabitation rather than just another good to demand from the state (Stavrides and Travlou, 2022, pp. 1-2). The work of Stavros Stavrides in particular has been influential here, as he invites us to imagine a “city of thresholds” that opens to alterity and difference through its “shared heterotopias,” in the place of the dominant “city-of-enclaves” model obsessed with segregation and control (Stavrides, 2016; see also Stavrides and Travlou, 2022). On the other hand, housing scholars and activists from various countries in the region: former Yugoslavia, Hungary, Greece, Lithuania, etc. have also mobilized the historical experience of East European socialism as a political and epistemic resource, in their work against evictions,

foreclosures, and the forced removal of vulnerable populations. Part of that mobilization has included efforts to resignify phenomena such as societal housing, worker self-management, and the robust relations with the former Third World through the Non-Aligned Movement, including in the field of housing (Jovanović, 2022; Vilenica, Florea, Popovici, and Pósfai, 2021). Attention has also been drawn to (now devalued and even vilified) bottom-up practices such as the Yugoslav *moba* and the Soviet *blat*, respectively a customary-law practice of building houses communally and a form of redistribution of wealth through self-organized pilfering of resources from one's workplace, as both reflecting and helping produce non-capitalist senses of self-in-community (Vilenica, 2023, Naujininkai Commons Collective, 2023).

Finally, this special issue contributes to growing and influential debates on the “global urban” and comparative urbanism within the social sciences as well. Spurred on by the intervention by postcolonial and decolonial theorists, this still relatively new methodology calls for a search for a new “geography of theory” and a “thinking from elsewhere” in its practice of “comparative imagination” (Robinson, 2021; Chelsea, Ferenčuhová, and Bădescu, 2021; Hirt et al., 2024). Its ambition, as argued by Jennifer Robinson recently, has been to propose a “thick and dynamic research practice which calls for careful attention to different contexts, to the diverse positionalities and concerns of researchers, and to the dynamism of concept formation” (Robinson, 2021, p. 97). Notably, the challenge posed by this type of urbanism is not only against the presumed epistemological supremacy of the Global North, with its North Atlantic universals, but also against a perhaps all-too-quick substitution of the South as a meta-theoretical reference point. As they invite us to think outside the “West versus the rest” binary, Martin Müller and Elena Trubina for instance have proposed refocusing the attention of urban studies also on the cities in the interstices of the former “Second World,” relegated since the end of the Cold War to the status of a “gray zone” of non-existence and irrelevance. For Müller and Trubina such a refocusing on what they theorize as a plurality of “Global Easts” reconstitutes the latter as a “unique conceptual resource” and may also serve as an emancipatory project redressing past erasures and establishing a subject position for the East and for East European scholars (Müller and Trubina, 2020, 2). Different from if possibly complementary to a political economic analysis, this type of global comparative urbanism poses the question of the “geopolitics of knowledge” (Müller and Trubina, 2020, 3).

The above debates constitute, of course, only a fragment of the variegated landscape of theorizing about and organizing in the post-socialist cities of Eastern Europe. Yet the scholars and activists who have contributed to these lines of inquiry help us not only fine-tune our

analysis of the regional urban area but also give us a felt sense of hope and possibility, in these otherwise bleak times. In an Eastern Europe that, for thirty-five years now, has been a radical laboratory of neoliberal depredation and violence, attentiveness to the deep intersections of class and urban struggles and the inseparability of production and reproduction, along with a refusal of epistemic mimicry, not only nuances the theoretical understanding of a transition that, in a way, never really was. More importantly, such attentiveness and refusal also galvanize the radical imagination and help counter an all-too-familiar and often hard-to-resist political (because also theoretical) paralysis.

The Dossier and its Texts

The articles in this special issue deal with, accordingly, what we may call (after Lefebvre and Harvey) “the Right to the city,” the (right to) housing (as foundational urban commons, as per Stavrides), and an effort to restore epistemic dignity to (the study of) East European cities from the perspective of a truly global comparative urban. They constitute collectively a fine mix of theoretical sophistication and activist commitment, while their authors span the gamut from professional architects to housing activists to scholars of urbanism. The methodologies deployed include activist-oriented discussions of the capacity of socially engaged architecture to also produce effects of self-making and transformation, a repurposed political economic analysis of the city and of housing under post-socialism, and a comparativist approach inspired by postcolonial theorizing. While highly critical of the erosion of the urban fabric under neoliberalism and the ideologies that subtend it, the texts also gesture toward solutions and alternative arrangements.

The issue begins with Sonja Dragović’s discussion of socialist engaged architecture under post-socialism, in which she explores progressive architectural practices in modern-day Croatia. Working against the tide of a competitive market and the politics of austerity of neoliberalism, socially engaged architecture challenges the depoliticized role of architects as providers of services and promotes an understanding of space as a common resource meant to serve local communities. In her text, Dragović looks at three instances of such architecture: the Pula Group/Cooperative Praksa, ARCHIsquad from Zagreb, and the Split Society of Architects. All three have brought awareness of the spatial dimensions of urban inequalities and have also prioritized working with marginalized communities, often pro bono. Working within yet against the system of neoliberal capitalism, they also bring up the crucial question of scaling up such counter-hegemonic work.

In their article on the infrastructural barriers of the city of Sofia, Teodora Stefanova, Ina Valkanova, and Pavel Yanchev explore in turn the effects of urbanization and industrial development in the Bulgarian capital. Unlike the circular metabolism within the Sofia valley until the end of the 19th century, the city's subsequent rapid industrialization and urban growth completely unsettled this dynamic equilibrium. More specifically, the authors explore how the construction of infrastructural barriers such as riverbeds, boulevards, and especially railway lines has led to deep segregation between the more affluent South and the poorer North. The discussion of the Hristo Botev neighborhood, home to an impoverished population with racialized stigma attached, provides a case in point. As members of the activist architectural collective Gradoscope, the authors also discuss practices and activities they have been involved in with other city institutions, to improve access and reverse the segregatory patterns in the city.

In her text on the housing question in Romania, with a particular focus on the city of Cluj-Napoca as a specific case study, Enikő Vincze juxtaposes the centralized planning strategies of the Romanian socialist state with the de-planning tendencies of post-socialism. She demonstrates that under socialism the state invested heavily in housing for its rapidly urbanizing and industrializing population, while also allowing for a mixed-housing regime under the high cost of socialist governmentalism. The centralized Romanian state also refused to separate the processes of production and social reproduction, reinvesting the produced social surplus into collective consumption goods such as schools, hospitals, and housing. Under the pressures of neoliberalism, however, state and municipal governments have effectively deregulated the housing market and adopted a “polycentric development” model leading to growing spatial and social inequalities. “Smart cities” such as Cluj-Napoca (often referred to as the Silicon Valley of Eastern Europe) embody these contradictory logics via their chaotic and often racialized patterns of urban growth.

In their discussion of housing financialization in Hungary, Zsuzsanna Pósfai and Martin Sokol look at three periods of this phenomenon, starting respectively in 2008, 2015, and 2022. While the period between 2008 and 2015 was one debt default mitigation and external foreign dependency, the year 2015 initiated a housing boom, spurred on by state subsidies such as the “Baby Expecting Loan” that both strengthened the middle-class support base of the Fidesz party and benefited local banks and construction companies. The period after 2022 has seen a re-emergence of foreign-dependent financialization, as the return of foreign buyers and a spike in rental prices also led to an increase in class-based and spatial inequalities. As they look

toward an uncertain future for the housing market in Hungary, Pósfai and Sokol call for the need to recognize new and more cooperative forms of housing tenure.

Last but not least, Sonia Hirt draws on Charles Tilly's taxonomy of comparative research to revisit the debate on the East European city from a comparative urbanist perspective. While, in her telling, the work on the socialist city was dominated alternatively by the historical and the ecological schools of urbanism, both schools took the Western city as an implicit model of analysis. The partial and highly interesting exception to this pattern was the writing of Soviet urbanists who saw the "sotsgorod" as an autonomous entity. Since the end of the Cold War, the pattern of comparison with the West has continued, even if the post-socialist city is now seen as an instance of accelerated, rather than delayed urbanism. Hirt asks what it would take for scholars to rupture this pattern of epistemological mimicry and suggests that the empirical realities of the socialist city of the past may offer important cues toward such a project.

The dossier thus moves from two discussions of socially engaged architecture, including by architects, on to questions of housing, housing financialization and the cost of the privatizing strategies of neoliberal capital, to end with an examination of the post-socialist city's role within the comparativist turn of urban studies. While the methodologies often overlap (one cannot really separate urban (de-)planning from differentiated access to housing, nor a critique of the colonial structure of knowledge production from those of capitalist accumulation), the texts seek to not only probe the cumulative effects of the neoliberal transition but to also point to alternatives and efforts to imagine the city differently. We see the contributions to this issue as theoretical and political interventions on not only the kinds of cities we live in, but also on the types of urban environments we would like to be able to call home.

A Few Final Clarifications

We end this introduction with two brief notes, one conceptual, the other historical.

The conceptual note concerns the words in the title. Scholars have aptly documented the increasing vacuousness and theoretical inadequacy of post-socialism as a concept, especially with the early charms and empty promises of the "transition" now long gone. For all its deficiencies, however, *post-socialism* still retains a more than etymological connection to a not-so-distant past, that of historically existing socialism, which continues to be under heavy attack to this day. *Inequality*, of course, needs little explaining, in the Eastern half of a continent that has seen both an explosion of (not only urban) poverty and a rapidly growing socio-economic gap between the (few) haves and the (many) have-nots. Perhaps most

importantly, and most extensively discussed (including with one of our authors), the final four words in the title, including the preposition, the definite article, and the purposeful choice of bracketing, raise a series of complex questions. We self-consciously pursue a few cumulative if hard-to-reconcile effects with that final word choice. For starters, (the unbracketed) “*taking power*” is meant as a challenge to the temptation of pure horizontalism (of the John Holloway type), especially in a region with a mixed, i.e. not just abortive, legacy of state socialism, the additional preposition “back” pointing to both that historical experience and the memory wars it has been implicated in. By the same token, the definite article in “taking (back *the*) power” seeks to contest easy assumptions about urban transformation as solely the result of top-down policies and institutional decision-making, accentuating instead “having *the* power” to do something, individually or collectively, rather than “taking *power*” so it can be exercised by institutional fiat over others. The admittedly awkward phrasing of that final part of the title seeks to preserve, in an openly dialectical manner, the irreducible contradiction between top-down practices and bottom-up pressures, both of which are likely to have a role to play in a future transformation of the “post-socialist” city.

The historical note is about the pre-history of the 2022 Sofia Forum on Urban Inequalities which led to this issue. In summer 2021, one of us (Nikolay Karkov) witnessed a shocking racist incident aboard the well-publicized Rhodope tesnolineika (narrow-gauge) train traversing parts of the Bulgarian south-western countryside, as a young boy was about to be removed from the train for lacking 2 lv (about \$1 in local currency) for his ticket. While the danger was averted, at the soon-to-follow dinner with the Collective for Social Interventions the idea was floated to organize a conference and a series of workshops in one of the small multicultural locales where the young boy and his two underage companions came from. Logistical and financial reasons prevented this plan from coming to fruition, as we ended up choosing Sofia instead. Yet the incident and its follow-up illustrate well some of the major stakes in this dossier of texts as well: the frequent morphing of ethnicity into race as a lived modality of class (Hall et al, 1982), the inseparability of the metropole from its impoverished (and often racialized) hinterland, and the overall imperative of thinking and organizing against racial capitalism (Robinson, 2000) on multiple fronts and scales. While this is a special issue on the post-socialist city, both we as editors and our authors would surely agree that thinking about the city also entails thinking about the material (political, economic, cultural, etc.) conditions that make that city possible as a complex, contradictory, and multi-layered terrain of transformation and struggle. Writing about the city is thus also about writing about the city’s

“other,” being cognizant of both their interdependence and the need to challenge their hierarchy.

We should add finally that, while aware of the pitfalls of deferential politics (Táíwò, 2022) and having little control over the matter of the actual submissions, we as editors also recognize that a wider plurality of voices (minoritized scholars for instance) would have strengthened the issue beyond its current shape and content.

References

- Chelsea, L., & Ferenčuhová, S., & Bădescu, G. (2021). Globalizing Postsocialist Urbanism. In M. Lancione & C. McFarlane (Eds.), *Global Urbanism: Knowledge, Power and the City* (pp. 71-79). Routledge.
- Engels, F. (1987). *The Condition of the Working Class in England*. Penguin.
- Hall, S., & Critcher, C., & Jefferson, T., Clarke, J., & Roberts, B. (1978). *Policing the Crisis: Mugging, the State, and Law and Order*. Macmillan Press.
- Harvey, D. (2019). *Rebel Cities: From the Right to the City to the Urban Revolution*. Verso.
- Hirt, S. (2012). *Iron Curtains: Gates, Suburbs and Privatization of Space the Post-Socialist City*. Wiley-Blackwell.
- Hirt, S., Grgić, Ž., Shaffer, Y. (2024). The East European Socialist/Post-socialist City as a Comparative Endeavor: Rethinking Our Research Perspective. In *European Journal of Spatial Development (EJSD)* 21(5), (pp 107-118).
- Iles, A. (2023). From the Neoliberal City to Disaster Capitalism, from Commons to “Unenclosure.” In M. Taylor & N. Brehmer (Eds.), *The Communist Horizon: Futures Beyond Urbanization* (pp. 39-82). Common Notions.
- Kanavaris, N. (2022). Refugee Housing Squats as Shared Heterotopias: The Case of City Plaza Athens Squat. In S. Stavrides & P. Travlou (Eds.), *Housing as Commons: Housing Alternatives as Response to the Current Urban Crisis* (pp. 162-190). Bloomsbury.
- Katerini, T. (2022). A Greek Activist’s Reflections on the Housing Struggles and the Movement Against Foreclosures in Athens. In Stavrides S., & Travlou P. (Eds.), *Housing as Commons: Housing Alternatives as Response to the Current Urban Crisis* (pp. 233-241). Bloomsbury.
- Lefebvre, H. (2003). *The Urban Revolution*. University of Minnesota Press.
- Lefebvre, H. (2000). *Writings on Cities*. Blackwell.
- Müller, M., & Trubina, E. (2020). The Global Easts in Global Urbanism: Views from Beyond North and South. *Eurasian Geography and Economics*, 1-9, DOI: 10.1080/15387216.2020.1777443
- Naujininkai Commons Collective (Aglinskas, V., & Stepanovaite, V., and Brehmer N.) (2023). Capital’s Social Fix: Divestment and Agency in the Post-Socialist Regenerate City. In M. Taylor & N. Brehmer (Eds.), *The Communist Horizon: Futures Beyond Urbanization* (pp. 123-154). Common Notions.
- Reclus, E. (2013). *Anarchy, Geography, Modernity: Selected Writings of Élisée Reclus*. PM Press.
- Robinson, C. (2000). *Black Marxism: The Making of the Black Radical Tradition*. University of North Carolina Press.
- Robinson, J. (2021). Comparative Urbanism and Global Urban Studies: Theorizing the Urban. In M. Lancione & C. McFarlane (Eds.), *Global Urbanism: Knowledge, Power and the City* (pp. 96-104). Routledge.
- Simmel, G. (1950). The Metropolis and Mental Life. In K. Wolf (Ed.), *The Sociology of Georg Simmel* (pp. 409-424). Free Press.
- Stavrides, S. and P. Travlou. (2022). Introduction: Revisiting the Housing Question: The Potentialities of Urban Commoning. In S. Stavrides and P. Travlou (Eds.), *Housing as Commons: Housing Alternatives as Response to the Current Urban Crisis* (pp. 1-18). Bloomsbury.
- Táiwò, O. (2022). *Elite Capture: How the Powerful Took Over Identity Politics (And Everything Else)*. Haymarket books.
- Vilenica, A. (2023) Who Has “The Right to Common”? Decolonizing Commoning in East Europe. In M. Taylor and N. Brehmer (Eds.), *The Communist Horizon: Futures Beyond Urbanization* (pp. 11-38). Common Notions.

Vilenica, A., & Florea, I., & Popovici, V., & Pósfai, Z. (2021). Urban Struggles and Theorizing from Eastern European Cities: A Collective Interview with Ana Vilenica, Ioanna Florea, Veda Popovici, and Zsuzsi Pósfai. In M. Lancione and C. McFarlane (Eds.), *Global Urbanism: Knowledge, Power and the City* (pp. 306-326). Routledge.